

Studies on Dakin Reaction

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Dakin reaction has been studied with a number of unsubstituted and substituted aromatic aldehydes where the substituents are either electron releasing or electron withdrawing groups. It has been observed that the conversion of aldehydes to phenols requires an intermediate quinonoid structure the formation of which is facilitated by hydroxyl groups occupying ortho or para to aldehydic function. Incidentally, it has been observed that 3-formyl indole under Dakin condition furnishes indigo in almost quantitative yield.

It was reported by Dakin¹ that ortho or para hydroxy benzaldehyde or acetophenone upon oxidation with alkaline hydrogen peroxide furnish the corresponding phenols. To rationalise the mechanistic pathway of these reactions it was thought appropriate to study the action of alkaline hydrogen peroxide with unsubstituted aromatic aldehydes or such compounds having *o*, *m* and *p*-substituents which are either electron releasing or electron withdrawing. For the purpose a number of compounds were selected (Vide Chart I) which were treated with alkaline hydrogen peroxide. Compounds (1-7) underwent Dakin reaction to yield the expected phenolic products while the results were negative with compounds (8-14). The compounds (5-7), though investigated by Dakin, were re-examined in order to correlate the results and to rationalise therefrom the pathway through which Dakin's reaction will proceed.

A number of mechanisms^{2,3} were postulated earlier to explain Dakin reaction of which Dakin's original explanation¹ appears to be the most satisfactory. Although Dakin did not enunciate any rational mechanism, he, however, emphatically stated that the formation of phenolic products from aromatic aldehydes is accentuated by the intervention of quinonoid structures. This is quite plausible because a hydroxyl group ortho or para to the aldehyde function generally facilitates Dakin's reaction, the hydroxyl groups presumably being involved in quinonoid forms in alkaline medium as evidenced from spectroscopic data⁴. Convincing evidence regarding the intermediate quinonoid structures have been secured by the present authors and a suitable mechanism for Dakin's reaction has been postulated.

1. H. D. Dakin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **XVIII**, 474.
2. Jack Hine, "Physical Organic Chemistry", p. 324, McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York, Toronto, London, 1956.
3. A. J. Cram and G. S. Hammond, "Organic Chemistry", p. 458, McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York, Toronto, London, 1959.
4. A. I. Scott, "Interpretation of the Ultraviolet Spectra of Natural Products", Pergamon Press Ltd., Oxford, 1964.

The steps involved in the reaction are first initiated by nucleophilic attack by hydroperoxide anion at the carbonyl carbon followed by an intramolecular nucleophilic displacement through phenonium participation giving rise to an intermediate epoxide and subsequent rearrangement of the epoxide to the formyl ester and hydrolysis of the formyl ester to the phenolic product.

The greater yield of phenolic compounds with ortho or para hydroxy benzaldehyde can thus reasonably be explained on the basis of the greater stability and the ease of formation of the species (I) and the ease of phenonium participation of (I) to yield the epoxide (II).

But in the case of benzaldehyde or anisaldehyde, the yield is extremely poor because of the relatively unfavourable situation for the phenonium participation in the initial intermediate to give the similar epoxides (III) and (IV) respectively.

Application of Dakin reaction on 3-formyl indole was found to be quite interesting as the latter furnished indigo in almost quantitative yield. The formation of the latter obviously involves indoxyl as the obligatory intermediate which through oxidative coupling produces indigo. The formation of indoxyl essentially follows the same sequence of steps as outlined in the previous case and the reason for the greater yield of the reaction product is due to the fact that the structural requirements essential for the success of Dakin reaction are excellently satisfied by the benzopyrrole moiety of 3-formyl indole as depicted below :

It has been indicated earlier that compounds (8-14) did not respond to Dakin reaction at all. The reason for the failure of compounds (8-10) to give phenolic products is due to the electron withdrawing effects of the nitro groups. In spite of having the necessary electron releasing groups, the reluctance of compounds (11-13) to undergo Dakin reaction may be presumably due to the prepondering side reactions such as oxidation involving the lone pair of nitrogen which inhibit the formation of quinonoid structures. The failure of piperonal to Dakin reaction could be explained due to the extreme instability of the intermediate quinonoid species (V) essential for the feasibility of the reaction.

CHART I

No.	Substrate and amount	Amount of H ₂ O ₂ (3%)	Phenolic product and its molecular formula	M.P. (solvent) and % yield of the Product	Analysis			
					% Found		% Calculated	
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	C	H	C	H
					(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
1.	Benzaldehyde 26.5 g.	342 ml	Phenol, C ₆ H ₆ O	— 0.5	75.90	5.58	76.50	6.30
2.	Anisaldehyde 30.0 g.	280 „	<i>p</i> -Methoxy phenol, C ₇ H ₈ O ₂	— 0.8	67.30	6.15	67.74	6.45
3.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde 11.5 g.	133 „	Hydroquinone, C ₆ H ₆ O ₂	170° (benzene) 80	64.85	5.25	65.45	5.45
4.	3-Formylindole 1.5 g.	14 „	Indigo	388-90° (dec) (chloroform) 70	73.00	3.62	73.27	3.84
5.	Salicylaldehyde 5.7 g.	66.2 „	Catechol, C ₆ H ₆ O ₂	104° (benzene) 85	64.90	5.20	65.45	5.45
6.	5-Bromosalicylaldehyde 5.09 g.	32.0 „	5-Bromocatechol, C ₆ H ₅ O ₂ Br	86° (petrol ether) 75	37.85	2.35	38.09	2.64
7.	Vanillin 4.0 g.	40 „	<i>m</i> -methoxy hydroquinone, C ₇ H ₈ O ₂	82-83° (benzene) 72	67.32	6.18	67.74	6.45
8.	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde 8.0 g.	68.30 „	No phenolic product	—	—	—	—	—
9.	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde 4.0 g.	34.16 „	No phenolic product	—	—	—	—	—
10.	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde 1.0 g.	8.54 „	No phenolic product	—	—	—	—	—
11.	<i>o</i> -Aminobenzaldehyde 10.0 g.	78.5 „	No phenolic product	—	—	—	—	—
12.	<i>p</i> -Aminobenzaldehyde 8.0 g.	63.0 „	No phenolic product	—	—	—	—	—
13.	<i>p</i> -Diethylamino benzaldehyde 10.0 g.	70.5 „	No phenolic product	—	—	—	—	—
14.	Piperonal 5.0 g.	43.0 „	No phenolic product.	—	—	—	—	—

The Dakin reaction is most probably ionic rather than radical as postulated above has been supported by the fact that by bubbling air for several hours through alkaline or neutral solution of 3-formyl indole or hydroxy aromatic aldehyde, we failed to detect any trace of the expected product. Further addition of reagents e.g., FeSO_4 which facilitate the generation of radical was found to have negligible effect on the percentage yield of the reaction product.

EXPERIMENTAL

General Procedure for Compounds other than 3-formyl indole: Substrate in alkali (molar proportion) was allowed to react with hydrogen peroxide at room temperature or under reflux in an inert atmosphere (N_2 gas) for 15 minutes to 1 hour depending upon the nature of the substrate. The mixture was then cooled, acidified with HCl to pH 5 and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was shaken with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate to remove any acid formed and then treated with caustic soda solution to free it from any unreacted substrate. The alkali-soluble portion was separated, acidified with HCl and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, then with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of ether afforded the corresponding phenolic products as shown in Chart 1. The products have been identified by their undepressed mixture melting point determinations with authentic samples.

Indigo from 3-formyl indole: To a solution of 3-formyl indole (1.5 g.) in caustic soda solution (1N, 10.5 ml.) was added hydrogen peroxide (3%, 14 ml) at room temperature. After 10 min. indigo separated out from alkaline solution. It was filtered at the pump, washed with hot water and crystallised from chloroform in the form of dark blue powder, m.p. 388–90° (dec.) (yield 70.0%) [Found: C, 73.00; H, 3.62; N, 10.55; Calc. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$: C, 73.27; H, 3.84; N, 10.68].

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